

During my residency with the collective @maisunomaisum in Talude, I noticed different reactions from cis men and women when I talked about the research-intervention. When I spoke with women, they often responded with a smile, requiring little explanation. Men, however, tended to remain silent, waiting for more... This makes things challenging, as engaging men is crucial to the project. Of course, their lack of engagement is a response in itself. During my residency with the collective @maisunomaisum in Talude, I noticed different reactions from

RESEARCH RESIDENCY

PAI DERIVA was an immersion proposed by Brazilian researcher Rodrigo Édipo Silva, selected through the open call PLAY(THE)GROUND - INFORMALITY AS RESISTANCE, organized by the collective mais uno +1. The residency took place in September 2024 in Talude, a social neighborhood in Lisbon where the majority of the population consists of Cape Verdean immigrants.

The project aimed to map informal oral and bodily repertoires that co-emerge from the interactions between fathers and children as they wandered aimlessly through the neighborhood.

With the child leading the way, the goal was to find clues for the re-enchantment of everyday life and the emancipation from disciplinary territories, with fatherhood symbolically being one of them.

Organization / Editing / Revision

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Production

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Support

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CHILDREN, WITH THEIR NATURAL OPENNESS AND CURIOSITY, ARE LIKE BRIDGES IN NURTURING THIS RELATIONSHIP. THEY CREATE INFORMAL SPACES WHERE AUTHENTICITY FLOURISHES, ALLOWING THE DISSOLUTION OF BARRIERS AND MORE MEANINGFUL EXCHANGES.

"Talude through the Eyes of Children" is the name of the walk we will be doing this Saturday (09/13).

These past days here at the residence have been spent planning the activity with the children, encouraging adults, especially fathers, to participate, and seeking support from local businesses for the event. In the images, I introduced the children to Google Earth, where we could virtually walk through Talude and the wider region of Catujal. During our virtual navigation, the children showed me various places, pointed out where they study, and made plans for the routes they want to show the adults during tomorrow's walk. "Talude thr

RIO TRANCÃO

RIO TRANCÃO
Texto do seu parágrafo

TALUDE

Emotional map of Talude: Marianne Delaforge

This real-life walk holds a deep sense of belonging for the children, as they eagerly anticipate sharing the places that are part of their daily lives. It is a chance to not only showcase their environment but also strengthen the connections between family, community, and the spaces they call home. The excitement is palpable as they prepare to lead this meaningful journey through the familiar paths of their world.

A black and white photograph of a person playing a pandeiro in a favela. The person is in the center, wearing a light-colored shirt and dark pants, playing a pandeiro. They are surrounded by other people, including children and adults, who are looking at them. The background shows a dense, informal settlement with buildings and a street. The text is overlaid on the image in a large, white, sans-serif font.

I take my pandeiro and play the few rhythms I know as I walk through the streets. As I begin to draw attention, smiles, and curious glances, I stop and chat with children, adults, and older people. This is how I learn many stories, some enchanting and others less so.

A black and white photograph of a child's hand reaching out to touch a large, textured rock formation. The child's hand is on the right side of the frame, with fingers extended towards the rock. The rock surface is highly textured with many small, dark spots and crevices. The background is a blurred, natural setting with more rocks and foliage.

On the first day of the residency, the children took me on a frenetic and labyrinthine walk to explore the Talude neighborhood. We passed through alleyways, visited a demolished house—which they referred to as an abandoned house complete with scary stories, although it turned out to be nothing more than a cat's tail moving among the rubble. We went to one child's grandfather's house, where there were sugarcane and pigs, and also visited other relatives' homes because the children were eager to introduce me to everyone.

During the walk, we were accompanied by a dog named Zito, who faithfully followed us. We picked fresh grapes, and I tried some Cape Verdean snuff with friends I made along the way. Throughout the walk, we were joined by a father, some uncles, and cousins. Since it was a weekday, many others were at work. The challenge of involving fathers and adult men in informal activities with the children is what has intrigued us most during the residency. The idea is to come up with various ways to make these encounters happen more often. In addition to the children and adults from the community, we were accompanied by Jaqueline and Kalle.

“Maybe what you’re asking is too much,” a young man told me at a baptism celebration last Saturday. “In Cape Verde, fathers work hard, and a good father is one who takes responsibility—and that’s rare. Many leave the mother to handle everything,” he explained. “I used to criticize my father, but now I understand where he came from.”

Recently, I tried to engage two fathers from the community. It felt awkward, as they were in the middle of laying concrete when I arrived, invited by a family member. During their break, I asked for an introduction in Creole before speaking myself. "He wants to do an activity with the children on Saturday or Sunday and invites you," was the introduction. Silence followed. The two fathers simply looked at me. I began to explain, but the more I spoke, the quieter the atmosphere became. Later, my local contact, a Cape Verdean father, laughed with me about the experience.

In the article "Casa sem homem é um navio à deriva," Cape Verdean anthropologist Celeste Fortes explains that women are central to family life, managing both the household and child care. Despite their efforts, they operate within a framework that idealizes the nuclear, patriarchal family, with men's caregiving roles remaining secondary.

At the residence in Talude, we, the resident artists, have free access to the AMRT space (the local association), which is located right at the entrance of the neighborhood. It's a large space where the community usually holds their celebrations, but during the week, it hasn't been used for other activities. Over time, I felt the need to connect more with Talude and make the street my studio/workspace. So, I decided to take some walks around the neighborhood, talking to people at the doorways of their homes.

One of the people who has welcomed me warmly here is Santos, the owner of the only bar in Talude, which, to me, is much more than just a bar; it's an authentic space of musical resistance.

There, Santos has a keyboard and a sound system, and whenever he feels like it, he plays funaná beats. "Music is my life," he has told me a few times in the short time we've known each other.

In this small space, there are a few armchairs, a television with blaring sound, a counter to serve customers, some posters of blonde women in beer advertisements, a Spider-Man poster, and many other details that make the environment magical. It's one of the spaces where I most closely feel what the atmosphere of Cape Verde might be like.

"Talude of the children, I'm really satisfied with them, I'm satisfied with them because they are... they are flowers of revolution. I'm remembering my childhood (in Cape Verde), when I was a child. I played and danced. I told stories. Everything." (Santos)

While interacting with some local friends, I was informed that the community was in mourning. A relative of a family deeply active in our residency activities, an elderly man, had passed away the day before. He had been living in Cape Verde. "In mourning, we don't make music," I was told. Since we had planned a joyful day, with music and dance after the walk, we decided it was best to cancel the activity out of respect for the grieving family and the funeral rites of their homeland. This moment made me reflect on how research and life are intertwined, and how a political perspective grounded in the ethics of care is essential in these spaces. In the process of research, a unique space of intimacy can form between the researcher and the world being studied. Built on trust, mutual respect, and deep engagement, this space allows the researcher to move beyond mere observation and fosters genuine connections that acknowledge the complexity of the community.

"Beginning, middle, and beginning," as the quilombola Nego Bispo says.

Talude pelo olhar das crianças

Despedida das férias

Voce ja parou para pensar que em Talude... ★

Existe uma casa abandonada que ja fez barulhos estranhos? E que um dia um cachorro ja abriu um portao com o nariz? E teve outro dia que...

Ah, venha descobrir estas e outras historias, deixando-se guiar pelo olhar encantado das crianças! ★

Caminhada em Talude

Duracao 40mn.

★ **Informações**

Sabado (14/09)
A partir das 14h30
Concentracao: AMAT

A black and white photograph of a makeshift structure made of metal sheets and pipes, with a utility tower in the background. The structure appears to be a temporary shelter or a small building under construction. The background shows a utility tower and some vegetation. The overall scene suggests a context of informal housing or a community in need of better living conditions.

As I prepare to return to Talude, after a period of respecting the community's request for introspection, I have been following the growing debates in Portugal about housing, a topic that deeply affects everyday life in Talude. The neighborhood, with its origins in clandestine construction and the occupation of peripheral lands in Lisbon, symbolizes both the struggle for housing and the resilience of its families, who have historically faced the specter of demolition and the uncertain promise of rehousing.

Yet, despite the instability in their living conditions, the families of Talude cultivate spaces of joy and resistance through their spontaneous, day-to-day interactions. Even in the face of challenges and the distancing of fatherhood from caregiving practices, I have observed that something within these relationships continues to be nurtured—particularly through music, celebrations, and not necessarily through walks.

In a context of housing crisis, dance and music paradoxically invite residents to inhabit another space-time—one that is more joyful and secure, capable of shaping collective subjectivities that do not deny the harsh reality but instead carve out a fold in time, where the ancestral Cape Verdean past inhabits the present and foreshadows the future.

PAIDERIVA